

Design and Characterization of Essential Components for a Magneto-Optical Trap

Rahul Das*

Abstract

This project is focused on the development and assembly of essential components for a Magneto-Optical Trap (MOT) used in ultracold atom experiments. Key tasks included constructing a mechanical shutter system to selectively block or allow the atomic beam into the trapping region, implementing a field-compensating Helmholtz coil to reduce background magnetic interference, and designing a radio-frequency antenna for evaporative cooling. These efforts contribute foundational tools for quantum control in ultracold atom research.

1 Introduction

A Magneto-Optical Trap (MOT) is a fundamental and widely utilized apparatus in atomic physics designed to cool and confine neutral atoms by exploiting the interaction between laser light and a spatially varying magnetic field. The MOT combines Doppler cooling, which reduces the kinetic energy of atoms via laser photon momentum exchange, with a quadrupole magnetic field that provides a position-dependent restoring force. This configuration enables atoms to be slowed down from thermal velocities and trapped at ultralow temperatures typically in the micro-Kelvin range.

MOTs serve as the foundational tool in the preparation of ultracold atomic samples, forming the initial stage for a variety of advanced experiments in quantum optics, atomic clocks, precision spectroscopy, and quantum simulation. The ability to precisely manipulate atomic motion and internal states using a MOT has revolutionized experimental atomic physics and has facilitated breakthroughs in fundamental science as well as in emerging quantum technologies.

*Corresponding author: rahul_20221111@students.iisertirupati.ac.in.

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3 Pneumatic cylinder

Initially, the design incorporated a motor in place of a pneumatic cylinder. However, after extended operation, the motor exhibited inefficiency due to coil heating, which adversely affected the shutter's performance. As a result, the system was revised to use a pneumatic cylinder, which offers a heavy-duty cycle and is capable of sustained operation over long periods without performance degradation.

3.1 How the pump works

3.1.1 Power Supply and Actuation Control

The solenoid coil of the valve is powered by a DC power supply (e.g., 24V). The return action is achieved using a spring inside the valve, which resets the spool to its default position when the coil is de-energized. Actuation is controlled via a switch or digital controller.

3.1.2 Initial State

In the initial stage, the solenoid is in the off position. The internal spring holds the spool in the default position.

3.1.3 Energized State (Solenoid ON)

The solenoid is energized and shifts the internal spool. Compressed air flows from Port P to Port A, causing the cylinder to extend (piston moves upward). Port B is vented to the atmosphere through Port S.

3.1.4 Initial State (Solenoid OFF)

While returning to the initial state, the solenoid is de-energized. The internal spring returns the spool to the initial position. The piston retracts due to air flowing into Port B again. Compressed air flows from Port P to Port B, causing the cylinder to retract (piston moves downward). Port A is vented to the atmosphere through Port R.

3.1.5 Mechanical Setup

The pneumatic cylinder is mounted vertically on an optical table using a metal base bracket. The cylinder rod points upward, and the body is fixed securely to prevent displacement during actuation. The 5/2 solenoid valve is fixed nearby using a mechanical support bracket.

3.2 Schematic Diagram

Figure 1: Schematic Diagram of the pneumatic cylinder

4 Earth's magnetic Field Compensator

The Earth's magnetic field causes distortions in the trapping step when the atom is inside the Molecular trap. The Earth's magnetic field is nullified using the square shaped Helmholtz coil. A square is preferred over circle to reduce the volume of the space occupied and that the coil gets fitted easily over the Optical table.

4.1 Calculating the Magnetic Field

4.1.1 Finding equations for the Square Helmholtz coil

In our case we have $z = L/2$ Using Biot Savart Law, vectorcially we can show,

$$B_x = \left(\frac{\mu_0 i L^2}{2\pi} \right) \left(\frac{1}{x^2 + \frac{L^2}{4}} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{x^2 + \left(\frac{L}{2}\right)^2}} \right) \quad (1)$$

Figure 2: Schematic figure of the square loop

Figure 3: Magnetic Field Comparison between 3 loops

We compared our formula with the known formulas for a circular coil of radius a and $\sqrt{2}a$.

We got the result as expected leading to our understanding that the equation should work properly.

The parameters we took here as, $N = 100$, $d = 0$, $a = 0.24\text{m}$, $I = 2\text{Amps}$, just for rough estimation.

[1] We now refer to this figure and do our calculations with respect to this,

Figure 4: Image of the Helmholtz square loops

Here we consider that the total length of one side of the coil is $2a$ and the total length of the distance between the two coils is $2d$

$$B_z = \left(\frac{N\mu_0 i 2a^2}{\pi} \right) \left[\left(\frac{1}{(z+d)^2 + a^2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{(z+d)^2 + 2a^2}} \right) + \left(\frac{1}{(z-d)^2 + a^2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{(z-d)^2 + 2a^2}} \right) \right] \quad (2)$$

We aim to cancel the Earth's magnetic field using a coil system. We begin by analyzing the magnetic field along one dimension (the z -axis), which can later be generalized to three dimensions.

Let

$$B_z^{\text{total}}(z) = B_z^{\text{coil}}(z) + B_z^{\text{earth}}, \quad (3)$$

where $B_z^{\text{earth}} \approx \text{const}$ near the origin.

To nullify the Earth's field, we want

$$B_z^{\text{total}}(z) = 0 \quad \text{in a region around } z = 0. \quad (4)$$

Since perfect cancellation at all points is not possible, we flatten the total field near the origin by requiring its derivatives to vanish:

$$\left. \frac{d^n B_z^{\text{total}}}{dz^n} \right|_{z=0} = 0 \quad \text{for } n = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (5)$$

Given B_z^{earth} is approximately constant,

$$\frac{d^n B_z^{\text{earth}}}{dz^n} = 0 \quad \text{for all } n \geq 1, \quad (6)$$

so we require:

$$\left. \frac{d^n B_z^{\text{coil}}}{dz^n} \right|_{z=0} = 0 \quad \text{for } n = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (7)$$

Now, expand $B_z^{\text{coil}}(z)$ in a Taylor series about $z = 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} B_z^{\text{coil}}(z) = & B_z^{\text{coil}}(0) + \left. \frac{dB_z^{\text{coil}}}{dz} \right|_{z=0} z + \frac{1}{2} \left. \frac{d^2 B_z^{\text{coil}}}{dz^2} \right|_{z=0} z^2 \\ & + \frac{1}{4!} \left. \frac{d^4 B_z^{\text{coil}}}{dz^4} \right|_{z=0} z^4 + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Due to symmetry of the coil configuration (two identical coils symmetrically placed about $z = 0$), the magnetic field is an even function of z , i.e.,

$$B_z^{\text{coil}}(z) = B_z^{\text{coil}}(-z), \quad (9)$$

which implies that all odd derivatives vanish at $z = 0$:

$$\left. \frac{d^{2n+1} B_z^{\text{coil}}}{dz^{2n+1}} \right|_{z=0} = 0. \quad (10)$$

We are thus left with the condition that all even-order derivatives vanish:

$$\left. \frac{d^2 B_z^{\text{coil}}}{dz^2} \right|_{z=0} = 0, \quad \left. \frac{d^4 B_z^{\text{coil}}}{dz^4} \right|_{z=0} = 0, \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

Imposing the condition

$$\left. \frac{d^2 B_z^{\text{coil}}}{dz^2} \right|_{z=0} = 0 \quad (12)$$

and solving for d/a , we obtain:

$$\frac{d}{a} = 0.5445. \quad (13)$$

This defines the Helmholtz condition, which ensures the second derivative of the magnetic field vanishes at the center, giving a flat field region around the origin.

4.1.2 The Helmholtz Configuration $d = 0.5445a$

[2]

Figure 5: Image of the Helmholtz Configuration square loop

We now plot the graph between the Magnetic field vs the spatial coordinate fixing some parameters and taking $d = 0.5445a$ [1]

Figure 6: Magnetic field vs spatial coordinates

The parameters we took here as, $N = 24$, $z = 0$, $a = 0.24\text{m}$, $I = 2.05\text{Amps}$ just for rough estimation.

In this equation,

$$B_z = \left(\frac{N\mu_0 i 2a^2}{\pi} \right) \left[\left(\frac{1}{(z+d)^2 + a^2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{(z+d)^2 + 2a^2}} \right) + \left(\frac{1}{(z-d)^2 + a^2} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{(z-d)^2 + 2a^2}} \right) \right] \quad (14)$$

We put $z = 0$, as we are interested to find the field in the center of the two coils. We start the evaluation with taking $a = 0.2\text{m}$ and a Magnetic field requirement for each coil to be 2 Gauss. We end up in the equation as, $N \times i = 49.1175$ turns-Amps.

4.1.3 The Cubical Configuration $d = a$

Figure 7: Image of the Cubical Configuration square loop

The parameters we took here as, $N = 43$, $z = 0$, $a = 0.24\text{m}$, $I = 2.01\text{Amps}$ just for rough estimation.

In the same way, we proceed with the calculations here and end up in the equation, $N \times i = 86.6$ turns-Amps.

Figure 8: Magnetic field vs spatial coordinates

4.1.4 Plots

Now we consider that $i \in [0, 5]$ and $i \in R^+$ and $N \in Z^+$ and we plot graphs for these two equations.

- $N \times i = 86.6$ turns-Amps.
- $N \times i = 49.1175$ turns-Amps.

And thus we get the plot,

Figure 9: Square Configuration vs The Helmholtz Configuration

In order to decide the correct configuration, we need to see the power emitted from both of the configuration, and take a particular value reducing the complexity and increasing the efficiency.

Thus we compare the two graphs with different i and N values and the power emitted by them respectively. These plots are only for one coil, so the power which we get is only for one coil with N turns.

Figure 10: Power vs N for Helmholtz configuration

Figure 11: Power vs N for Cubical configuration

From these 2 graphs we take the Helmholtz one which would be more relevant to use considering our parameters as it gives a uniform magnetic field in the trapping region, sufficient to compensate the Earth's magnetic field.

We take the value of, $N = 24, i = 2.05$ Amps.

Figure 12: Point selected

4.2 Heat Generation, Power Dissipation, and Temperature Fluctuation in a Resistive Wire

We analyze the thermal behavior of a resistive wire subjected to Joule heating and cooled via both radiative and convective mechanisms. The objective is to describe the time-dependent temperature evolution and identify the steady-state temperature under constant electrical input.

Joule Heating

The electrical power dissipated in the wire due to Joule heating is given by:

$$Q_{\text{gen}} = I^2 R \quad (15)$$

where:

- I is the current through the wire,
- R is the electrical resistance of the wire.

Radiative Heat Loss

The radiative power loss from the wire surface is described by the Stefan–Boltzmann law:

$$Q_{\text{rad}} = \epsilon \sigma A (T^4 - T_{\text{amb}}^4) \quad (16)$$

with the following parameters:

- ϵ is the emissivity of the wire surface,
- $\sigma = 5.670 \times 10^{-8} \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}^4$ is the Stefan–Boltzmann constant,
- A is the effective surface area of the wire,
- T is the temperature of the wire (in Kelvin),
- T_{amb} is the ambient temperature (in Kelvin).

Convective Heat Loss

Heat loss due to convection is governed by Newton’s law of cooling:

$$Q_{\text{conv}} = hA(T - T_{\text{amb}}) \quad (17)$$

where:

- h is the convective heat transfer coefficient ($\text{W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$),
- A is the surface area of the wire,
- T is the wire temperature,
- T_{amb} is the ambient temperature.

Total Heat Loss

Combining both radiative and convective losses, the total rate of heat loss from the wire becomes:

$$Q_{\text{loss}} = Q_{\text{rad}} + Q_{\text{conv}} = \epsilon\sigma A(T^4 - T_{\text{amb}}^4) + hA(T - T_{\text{amb}}) \quad (18)$$

Energy Balance and Time-Dependent Behavior

Using the principle of energy conservation, the rate of change of internal energy in the wire is the net heat input:

$$\frac{dQ}{dt} = \text{Power in} - \text{Power out} \quad (19)$$

The thermal energy of the wire is given by:

$$Q = mcT \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{dQ}{dt} = mc \frac{dT}{dt} \quad (20)$$

where m is the mass of the wire and c is the specific heat capacity of the material (e.g., copper).

Substituting Equations (15), (18), and (20) into Equation (19), the differential equation governing the wire temperature becomes:

$$mc \frac{dT}{dt} = I^2 R - \epsilon \sigma A (T^4 - T_{\text{amb}}^4) - hA(T - T_{\text{amb}}) \quad (21)$$

Steady-State Condition

At thermal equilibrium (steady state), the temperature of the wire no longer changes with time, i.e., $\frac{dT}{dt} = 0$. Equation (21) thus simplifies to:

$$I^2 R = \epsilon \sigma A (T^4 - T_{\text{amb}}^4) + hA(T - T_{\text{amb}}) \quad (22)$$

Comparative Analysis of Radiation and Convection

To assess the relative contribution of radiative and convective cooling, we define the dimensionless ratio:

$$\alpha = \frac{Q_{\text{conv}}}{Q_{\text{rad}}} = \frac{h(T - T_{\text{amb}})}{\epsilon \sigma (T^4 - T_{\text{amb}}^4)} \quad (23)$$

This quantity α is temperature dependent. We analyze α as a function of T to determine the regime in which radiative and convective losses become comparable, i.e., when $\alpha \approx 1$.

In our specific analysis, the following parameter values were used:

- Convective heat transfer coefficient: $h = 5.0 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$,
- Effective radiating surface area: $A = 0.4373 \text{ m}^2$, representing a bundle of copper wires with half of the total surface area exposed,
- Ambient temperature: $T_{\text{amb}} = 298 \text{ K}$.

A plot of α versus T provides insight into the dominant heat dissipation mechanism across the temperature range. When $\alpha = 1$, both radiation and convection contribute equally to thermal losses. The Graph we got was,

Figure 13: Alpha versus Temperature

So, we see that the temperature is 1316.15K (appx) which is extremely high and before that we can see that $\alpha \gg 1$, and thus we can neglect the Q_{rad} term. So we perform our calculations in steady state and with these approximations. The code for plotting α versus Temperature and The heat calculations are given in the end section. The calculations are done with uncertainties to ensure real/ physical scenario. Now putting values of the parameters and choosing AWG 56, we get,

All calculations are done here from the respect of 1 coil.

The Power radiated is :::: 1.641808 Watt

With an uncertainty of :::: 1.477627 Watt to 1.805989 Watt

The heat dissipated is :::: 59105.084578 Joule

With an uncertainty of :::: 53194.576120 Joule to 65015.593036 Joule

Temperature after time 36000 seconds is 295.7663507972516 K

We have considered the ambient temperature as 295 and after a time of 36000 seconds we get a temperature difference of 0.7663507972516186 K

If the Coils are turned on for 36000 seconds, then the temperature will vary from 295.5619905846512 K to 296.37943143505294 K

5 Antenna for the evaporative cooling step

5.1 1st Trial

We tried to build an antenna for the evaporative cooling step, like an LC Oscillator circuit using a bend metal strip. [3],

Figure 14: 1st trial of the Antenna

We formed the antenna by bending a copper strip of length l and width w . The inductance is approximated by the solenoid formula:

$$L = \frac{\mu_0 N^2 A}{l}, \quad (24)$$

where the strip is modeled as a solenoid, N is the number of turns, and A is the cross-sectional area. The capacitance is given by

$$C = \frac{\epsilon_0 A}{d}, \quad (25)$$

where A is the area of the capacitor plate and d is the separation between the plates. The resonance frequency is then

$$f = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{LC}}. \quad (26)$$

Figure 15: Schematic circuit of the antenna system.

Figure 16: Amplitude versus frequency (747–947 MHz).

A $50, \Omega$ resistor is incorporated into the circuit to ensure proper impedance matching with the pickup antenna. Impedance matching is crucial in RF systems to maximize power transfer and minimize signal reflections that can lead to losses or distortions in the received signal. By matching the antenna’s impedance to the characteristic impedance of the transmission line, the resistor helps maintain signal integrity across the system.

This analysis serves as a preliminary approximation of the antenna’s expected performance across a range of radio frequency (RF) fields. The resonance behavior observed, specifically the peak in power emission, aligns with the design intent, as the resonance frequency of the antenna’s LCR (inductor-capacitor-resistor) circuit was deliberately tuned within the band of 870 MHz to 900 MHz.

The presence of this resonance peak indicates the antenna’s ability to efficiently convert electromagnetic energy at the target frequency, which is vital for effective evaporative cooling procedures. Such cooling relies on precise RF field control to manipulate atomic states, and any mismatch or inefficiency in the antenna response could compromise the cooling dynamics.

5.2 Second Trial

Building upon insights from the initial trial, the second trial adopted a more analytical approach to antenna design by focusing on the calculation of the Rabi frequency [3]. The Rabi frequency quantifies the rate of coherent oscillations between atomic energy levels induced by the applied RF field and is a critical parameter in optimizing evaporative cooling and other quantum control techniques.

This approach allows for a more targeted antenna configuration, where the amplitude and spatial profile of the RF magnetic field can be engineered to produce desired transition rates. By directly relating antenna parameters to quantum mechanical interaction strengths, the design process becomes more predictive and efficient, paving the way for improved experimental outcomes.

Figure 17: Schematic of RF evaporation. Radiation with frequency ν_{RF} drives the $|2, 2\rangle \rightarrow |1, 1\rangle$ transition for atoms with sufficiently high energy. The RF frequency ν_{RF} is decreased over time, ejecting atoms and leaving only a small fraction of very cold atoms.

We have a Magnetic field Gradient of $\frac{dB}{dx} = 400$ Gauss/cm and we assume the trap nearly harmonic for the ease of calculations, so, we have,

$$U_{\text{kinetic}} = U_{\text{potential}} \tag{27}$$

$$K_B T = \mu_B B_{\text{trap}} \Rightarrow B_{\text{trap}} = \frac{K_B T}{\mu_B} \approx 1.384 \tag{28}$$

now, secondly we have,

$$\frac{1}{2}mv^2 = K_B T \Rightarrow v = \sqrt{\frac{2K_B T}{m_{\text{Lithium}}}} \approx 0.55 \text{ m/s} \quad (29)$$

Now,

$$B_{\text{trap}} \approx 1.54 = x \frac{dB}{dx} \approx 400 \text{ Gauss/cm} \times x \Rightarrow x \approx 0.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m} \quad (30)$$

$$\Rightarrow t = \frac{x}{v} \approx 10^{-4} \text{ secs} \quad (31)$$

and thus we have, frequency as,

$$\text{Freq} = \frac{1}{T} \approx 10 \text{ KHz.} \quad (32)$$

Now we go for calculating the Rabi frequency.

We know that $\Omega_{\text{Rabi}} \gg \text{Freq}$, so we assume $\Omega_{\text{Rabi}} \approx 1 \text{ GHz}$.

Now from the graph, we see,

$$|2, 2\rangle \rightarrow |1, 1\rangle \Rightarrow \Delta E = \Delta(m_F g_F) \mu_B B \approx (2g_{F=2} - 1g_{F=1}) \mu_B \quad (33)$$

$$\Rightarrow \Delta E = (1 + 1) \mu_B B \quad (34)$$

$$\Rightarrow 2\mu_B B \Rightarrow \Delta E = 2\mu_B B \quad (35)$$

So, now we have,

$$\Delta E = \hbar \Omega_{\text{Rabi}}, \quad \text{and thus, } 2\mu_B B_{\text{center}} = \hbar \Omega_{\text{Rabi}} \Rightarrow B_{\text{center}} = \frac{\hbar \Omega_{\text{Rabi}}}{2\mu_B} \quad (36)$$

$$\Rightarrow \mathbf{B}_{\text{center}} \approx 10 \text{ mG} \quad (37)$$

So, we need an antenna which will have a magnetic field of 10mG at the center of the MOT and with a high freq of $\approx 1 \text{ GHz}$.

[4] We have,

$$H_r \approx \frac{a^2 I_0 e^{-jkr}}{2r^3} \quad (38)$$

and $\mu_0 H_r = B$ for near field loop antennas ($kr < 1$), we have $\lambda = \frac{c}{f} \approx 30 \text{ cm}$ and $k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}$. Taking Real parts, we see,

$$\frac{\mu_0 I_0 a^2 \cos(kr)}{2r^3} = 10 \text{ mG} \quad (39)$$

Where a is the radius of the loop antenna and r is the distance of the atoms from the loop antenna and k is 20.94 rad/m.

We are given the expression for the magnetic field due to a loop antenna in the near field:

$$\frac{\mu_0 I_0 a^2 \cos(kr)}{2r^3} = B \quad (40)$$

In our case we have a distance

$$r = 16 \text{ mm} = 0.016 \text{ m},$$

from the atomic cloud to the antenna. And a loop of radius

$$a = 42 \text{ mm} = 0.042 \text{ m}.$$

Rewriting the expression and solving for I_0 :

$$I_0 = \frac{2r^3 B}{\mu_0 a^2 \cos(kr)} \quad (41)$$

First, compute kr :

$$kr = 20.94 \times 0.016 = 0.33504 \text{ rad} \quad (42)$$

$$\cos(kr) = \cos(0.33504) \approx 0.944 \quad (43)$$

After evaluating the whole problem, we get,

$$\boxed{\mathbf{I_0 \approx 0.003914 \text{ Amps or } 3.91 \text{ mA}}} \quad (44)$$

A current of approximately 3.91 mA is required in the frequency range of 800 MHz–1000 MHz to effectively drive the antenna. For antennas with a radius smaller than 42 mm, the required current for efficient radiation is expected to be even lower, which is advantageous. Although explicit calculations were not performed for each possible antenna radius, it can be reasonably estimated that the current remains on the order of milliamperes and does not deviate significantly from this reference value. While tuning across the wide frequency range of interest, minor fluctuations in current are acceptable and do not critically impact system performance, provided they remain close to the target value. Thus, achieving a plateau in the emitted RF power within the 800 MHz–1000 MHz band is crucial for ensuring reliable Majorana spin-flip transitions.

5.3 Trying out Combination of Different Antennas

Our objective is to design an antenna that emits power consistently across a plateau region approximately spanning 800 MHz to 1000 MHz. We explored various antenna configurations and evaluated their performance within this frequency range.

$$\text{Power emitted} = \text{Reflected to Signal/ Function Generator (SG/FG)} + \text{To Spectrum Analyzer (SA)} + \text{Wasted as heat} \quad (45)$$

Figure 18: Circuit for observing how much power went through the antenna after emission and reflection back due to impedance mismatch.

Figure 19: Circuit used to analyze the shape of the power emitted by the antenna.

We had several options for positioning the antenna:

- Inside the Bitter magnet (radius approximately 1.5 cm),
- Outside the Bitter magnet but inside the MOT chamber (radius approximately 3.5 cm-4 cm),
- Outside the MOT, near an optical window. However, in this configuration, the distance between the antenna and the atomic cloud would be significantly larger, requiring higher emitted power to effectively induce Majorana transitions.

The antenna was not placed inside the vacuum chamber. [3]

To identify the most suitable antenna configuration for RF cooling, various antenna designs were tested and compared. To streamline this process, I developed a custom Python-based interface that allowed simultaneous control of the signal generator and RF spectrum analyzer. This tool enabled real-time data acquisition and plotting, significantly enhancing the speed and efficiency of graphical analysis and comparison.

5.3.1 Small Loop vs. Large Loop Antenna (Parallel and Perpendicular)

We constructed a small single-loop antenna using copper wire and a coaxial cable. In both setups, the small loop acts as the radiating source and the large loop as the receiving antenna. (Refer Figure:19)

Two configurations were tested:

- **Parallel Configuration:** Both loops are positioned parallel to each other.
- **Perpendicular Configuration:** The large loop is oriented perpendicular to the small loop.

Figure 20: Comparison between parallel and perpendicular configurations of small loop (radiating) and large loop (receiving) antennas.

5.3.2 Strip Antenna and Small Loop Detector

A copper strip (10 cm \times 1 cm) was curved to form a radiating antenna. A small loop antenna (diameter 3 cm) was used as the detector. (Refer Figure:19)

Figure 21: Receiver placed 3 cm from strip antenna.

Figure 22: Receiver placed 1.5 cm from strip antenna.

Inside the Bitter Magnet

Figure 23: Strip antenna inside bitter magnet; receiver at 1.5 cm.

Figure 24: Strip antenna inside bitter magnet; receiver at 3 cm.

5.3.3 Strip Antenna with Capacitor and Loop Detector

A copper strip was curved to form a loop of the same dimensions, described in the previous case, and a capacitor was added using another copper strip placed nearby. (Refer Figure:19) (Same as described in the section of *1st Trial*).

Strip of 10cm * 1cm folded to form an antenna and a capacitor with it and a loop detector of diameter 3 cms placed at a distance of 1 cms

Figure 25: Strip antenna with capacitor; receiver at 1 cm.

Inside the Bitter Magnet

Strip of 10cm * 1cm folded to form an antenna with a capacitor placed inside a solenoid and a loop detector of diameter 3 cms placed at a distance of 1.5 cms

Figure 26: Strip antenna with a capacitor inside bitter magnet with loop detector at 1.5 cm.

5.3.4 Spiral Antenna with Loop Detector

A spiral antenna (7 loops, outer radius 3 cm, inner radius 1.5 cm) with loop detector of diameter 3 cm at varying distances. (Refer Figure:19)

(a) The Spiral Antenna

(b) Loop detector at 1.5 cm

(c) Loop detector at 2 cm

(d) Loop detector at 3 cm

Figure 27: Spiral antenna and loop detector measurements at 1.5 cm, 2 cm, and 3 cm distances.

5.3.5 Small Loop Antenna

We measured power passing through a small loop (radius 1.5 cm), after emission and power reflected back. (Refer Figure:18) (Refer Equation:42)

Figure 28: Loop connected to SG to track outgoing power.

Inside the Bitter Magnet

Figure 29: Loop inside bitter magnet connected to SG.

5.3.6 Small loop antenna With Pickup Antenna

Here, we observe the shape and values of the power of the small antenna as the previous case, however, we decided to make the receiving antenna, same as the dimension of the radiating antenna and we noted the values for different positions of the receiving antenna placed away from the radiating antenna. (Refer Figure:19)

Figure 30: Power distribution across distances (800 MHz-1000 MHz).

Inside the Bitter Magnet

Figure 31: Power emitted by the small loop antenna while placed inside the bitter magnet

Figure 32: Inside the bitter magnet with the loop detector same as the dimension of the radiating antenna

5.3.7 Large Loop Antenna

We measured power passing through a loop (radius 4 cm), after emission and power reflected back. (Refer Figure:18)(Refer Equation:42)

Figure 33: Large loop (4 cm radius) connected with the SA and SG.

5.3.8 Large Loop Antenna and a pickup antenna

Here we observe the power radiated by the large loop antenna of radius 4 cm using 2 pickup antennas of different dimensions. (Refer Figure:19)

Comparison: Small Pickup Antenna vs. Identical Pickup Antennas

Figure 34: Comparison between small multi-turn pickup loop and identical pickup antenna.

(a) Small, multi-turn pickup antenna (real image).

(b) Pickup antenna same as radiating (real image).

Figure 35: Two different pickup antenna configurations (real setup).

6 Conclusion

1. The operating principle of a pneumatic cylinder was analyzed, and its application as a mechanical shutter system was successfully implemented. This system enables selective blocking or passage of the atomic beam into the trapping region, offering precise control over atom flux into the Magneto-Optical Trap (MOT).
2. To compensate for the Earth’s magnetic field, a Helmholtz coil configuration was selected. After evaluating various design parameters, the optimal setup was determined to involve copper wire of gauge AWG 56, with the following specifications: number of turns $N = 24$, $a = 0.24\text{m}$, and operating current $I = 2.05\text{A}$. Detailed calculations supporting these parameters are presented in the section titled *Earth’s Magnetic Field Compensator*.
3. Radio-frequency (RF) antennas were evaluated for their suitability in facilitating evaporative cooling via spin-flip transitions. Both loop and strip-type antennas exhibited a plateau in RF emission between 800–1000 MHz. Additionally, it was observed that a strip antenna coupled with a capacitor could be tuned to achieve a similar plateau if the resonance frequency of the LCR circuit is positioned sufficiently far from the target range. Despite this flexibility, a significant limitation was the low power output in the desired frequency range, insufficient for driving spin-flip transitions efficiently. To address this, amplification of the RF signal from the signal/function generator is recommended. Furthermore, power tuning during experimental operation may be necessary, especially in frequency regions where the antenna response exhibits irregularities or troughs.

7 Acknowledgment

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8 Mathematical codes using python

8.1 For plotting Alpha versus Temperature

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from scipy.optimize import fsolve

# Constants
h = 5.0
A = 0.43730969737969916
epsilon = 0.03
sigma = 5.67e-8
T0 = 298

# Temperature array
T_vals = np.linspace(300, 5000, 10000)

# Alpha(T)
Q_conv = h * (T_vals - T0)
Q_rad = epsilon * sigma * (T_vals**4 - T0**4)
alpha_vals = Q_conv / Q_rad

# Find where alpha crosses 1 (zero crossing of alpha - 1)
alpha_diff = alpha_vals - 1
sign_changes = np.where(np.diff(np.sign(alpha_diff)))[0]

# Get the interval where alpha crosses 1
if len(sign_changes) == 0:
    print("No intersection found in the given range.")
else:
    i = sign_changes[0]
    T_low = T_vals[i]
    T_high = T_vals[i+1]

# Define equation alpha(T) - 1 = 0
def equation(T):
    Q_conv = h * (T - T0)
    Q_rad = epsilon * sigma * (T**4 - T0**4)
    return Q_conv / Q_rad - 1
```

```

# Use fsolve safely within this bracket
T_solution = fsolve(equation, x0=(T_low + T_high) / 2)[0]

# Plotting
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))
plt.plot(T_vals, alpha_vals, label=r'$\alpha(T)$', color='blue')
plt.axhline(y=1, color='red', linestyle='--', label=r'$\alpha = 1$')
plt.scatter(T_solution, 1, color='black', zorder=5)
plt.text(T_solution, 1.05, f'T = {T_solution:.2f} K', ha='center')
plt.xlabel('T (K)')
plt.ylabel(r'$\alpha(T)$')
plt.title(r'Solution of $\alpha(T) = 1$')
plt.grid(True)
plt.legend()
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

# Print result
print(f"Temperature T where alpha(T) = 1: T = {T_solution:.6f} K")

```

8.2 For Heat calculations of coil

```

import numpy as np
N = 24 #float(input("Say the number of turns :::::"))
I = 2.05 #float(input("Say the current we provide it in Amperes
:::::"))
half_side = 0.20 #float(input("Say the dimension of one side in
metres :::::"))
Radius = 0.000725 #float(input("Say the radius of the copper wire we
are using :::::"))
Time = 36000 #float(input("Time in seconds in which the device will
remain on :::::"))
Area = np.pi * (Radius)**2
rho_nominal = 1.68e-8
error_percent = 0.10 #float(input("Enter the error in decimal point

```

```

    for the resistivity of copper ( Mostly 0.10 ) :::::")
error_percent_C_v = 0.02 #float(input("Enter the error in decimal
    point for the C_v of copper ( Mostly 0.02 ) :::::")
error_percent_Density_of_copper = 0.01 #float(input("Enter the error
    in decimal point for the Density of copper ( Mostly 0.01 )
    :::::")
error_percent_in_emissivity = 0.55 # float(input("Enter the error in
    decimal point for the Emissivity of copper ( Mostly 0.55 )
    :::::")
error_percent_in_h = 0.5 #float(input("Enter the error in decimal
    point for the Convection coefficient of copper ( Mostly 0.5 )
    :::::")
rho_lower = rho_nominal * (1 - error_percent)
rho_upper = rho_nominal * (1 + error_percent)
length_of_one_loop = 4 * half_side * 2
total_length = N * length_of_one_loop
Volume = 2 * np.pi * Radius * total_length
Density_of_copper = 8960
mass_of_copper = Volume * Density_of_copper
C_v = 385
emissivity = 0.03
stefan_boltzmann_constant = 5.67e-8
T_ambient = 295
surface_area_exposed_to_radiation = np.pi * Radius * np.sqrt(N) *
    total_length
h = 5 # convective heat transfer coefficient (W/
    m2·K)
C_v_upper = C_v * (1 - error_percent_C_v)
C_v_lower = C_v * (1 + error_percent_C_v)
Density_of_copper_upper = Density_of_copper * (1 -
    error_percent_Density_of_copper)
Density_of_copper_lower = Density_of_copper * (1 +
    error_percent_Density_of_copper)
mass_of_copper_upper = Volume * Density_of_copper_upper
mass_of_copper_lower = Volume * Density_of_copper_lower
emissivity_upper = emissivity * (1 + error_percent_in_emissivity)
emissivity_lower = emissivity * (1 - error_percent_in_emissivity)
h_upper = h * (1 + error_percent_in_h)
h_lower = h * (1 - error_percent_in_h)
Resistance_upper = (rho_upper * total_length)/ Area

```

```

Resistance = ( rho_nominal * total_length / Area)
Resistance_lower = (rho_lower * total_length )/Area
Power_radiated = (I**2) * Resistance
Power_radiated_upper = (I**2) * Resistance_upper
Power_radiated_lower = (I**2) * Resistance_lower
Heat_dissipated = Power_radiated * Time
Heat_dissipated_upper = Power_radiated_upper * Time
Heat_dissipated_lower = Power_radiated_lower * Time
print(f"The Power radiated is :::::{Power_radiated:.6f} Watt")
print(f"With an uncertainty of ::::: {Power_radiated_lower:.6f} Watt
      to {Power_radiated_upper:.6f} Watt")
print(f"The heat dissipated is ::::: {Heat_dissipated:.6f} Joule")
print(f"With an uncertainty of ::::: {Heat_dissipated_lower:.6f}
      Joule to {Heat_dissipated_upper:.6f} Joule")
Temperature = (( Power_radiated ) / (h *
      surface_area_exposed_to_radiation)) + T_ambient
T_in_particular_upper = ((Power_radiated_upper) / ( h_upper *
      surface_area_exposed_to_radiation )) + T_ambient
T_in_particular_lower = ((Power_radiated_lower) / ( h_lower *
      surface_area_exposed_to_radiation )) + T_ambient
print("Temperature after time", Time,"seconds is ", Temperature,"K"
      )
print("We have considered the ambient temperature as", T_ambient,"
      and after a time of", Time,"seconds we get a temperature
      difference of", Temperature - T_ambient,"K")
print("If the Coils are turned on for ",Time,"seconds, then the
      temperature will vary from",T_in_particular_upper,"K to",
      T_in_particular_lower,"K")

```

References

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